

ISSUES OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE FORMATION OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. Social competence occupies an important place among the various forms of psychological competence studied by modern psychology. It also reflects the creative features of a person as a social partner, a cooperative subject. The mechanisms of formation of the subject's competent social behavior, manifestation tendencies, motivation, interest in the content, first of all, the character of "man-society" interaction is described by the influence on social prosperity and development. In this thesis, the issues of development of social competences in primary education students are considered.

Keywords: primary education, interpersonal relations, skills, social consciousness, innovative technologies, social competence, educational process, adaptation.

INTRODUCTION

The level of a person's social competence plays an important role in the process of establishing social flexibility, interaction, and activity.

In their research, psychologists have recognized that the formation of the level of social competence in people has a special place in the process of adaptation of citizens to the new social and globalization conditions. Environmental, political, ideological, and social changes not only determine the development of social thinking, but also affect people's self-concept, life values, and personal problems.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Organization and development of education in primary education on the basis of social competence is also based on the following basic principles of the State Education Standard [2]:

- the priority of the student's personality, his aspirations, abilities and interests;
- humanitarian content of general secondary education;
- Compliance of the state education standard with the requirements of the state and society in the field of education, as well as the needs of the individual;
- based on innovative technologies in choosing the content, form, means and methods of general secondary education;
- provision of the basis for students to study subjects and continue their education and development of general competences in subjects;
- to use the experience of setting standards in the field of education of developed foreign countries, taking into account national characteristics.

Based on the continuity and integrity of education, the priority of the student's personality and interests, and in accordance with their young characteristics, the following basic competencies from elementary grades [3]:

- Communicative competence
- Competence to work with information
- Competence of self-development
- Competence of a socially active citizen
- National and universal competence

RESULTS

Mathematical literacy, awareness and use of science and technology news are formed in students through general education subjects.

All students in groups of teachers, when students work in the field of social competence [4]:

- Participating and feeling part of the process.
- To agree on their goals and plans in order to achieve the desired results.
- To work on the sections allocated to them to achieve their results.
- Brainstorming on how to improve what they have done together.

It is necessary for them to talk about the work they have done and to ensure that they help each other in expressing their opinions.

The development of social competences is the education of future professionals who can meet the needs of more than just skills and business people.

On the basis of the development of social competences, the development of persons useful to the state and society, to involve them in maintaining national peace, to direct their activities to the interests of the people, to achieve meaningful spending of free time, to build a strong, fair, legal and democratic society. Implementation of educational tasks in the spirit of making the strengthening of the will to become an integral part of the lifestyle is considered one of the main tasks of higher education institutions.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The development of students' social competence, in turn, requires the determination of criteria guaranteeing the effectiveness of this process. These criteria are: the degree of formation of ideological and spiritual visions characterizing the level of awareness of social competence; level of acquisition of practical professional skills as necessary components of social competence; the level of development of social competence motivation; including independence and the level of development of initiative, resourcefulness, and entrepreneurship.

CONCLUSIONS

The social order facing education today is that it should not be limited to the formation of students' performance skills in the educational process. The complexity of the task is such that it is necessary to form the personal, inner foundations of behavior in students. In this practice, it is necessary to give the student the opportunity to show his personal qualities.

The student's personal qualities are the qualities that each person has in his own way, which show his attitude to general values, and have personal importance. They are cultured, creative, free, independent, having the opportunity to choose,

voluntary, international, personal creative, creative, unique, belonging to civil society, justice, discipline, solidarity, empathy. Fulfilling the above-mentioned requirements is a huge responsibility for every skilled and competent teacher.

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